

1 **PI3K controls homeostasis associated with energy in the cell.**

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6 We demonstrate here that engineered homozygous mutation of PI3K in human stem cells results in
7 collapse of cellular homeostasis. PI3K deficiency in human cells resulted in activation and otherwise broad
8 dysregulation of markers of cellular homeostasis including metallothionein responses genes (MT1F and
9 MT1X) that indicate cellular stress, molecules functioning in protein folding and global entropy of the
10 proteome like thioredoxin molecules TXNRD1/2 and peptidyl prolyl isomerase PPI family genes (PPIA,
11 PPFIA2), as well as dysregulation of more specific sensors of homeostasis like ferridoxin (FDX1) and
12 nucleoredoxin (NXN). An energy regulatory function of PI3K is required to manage dynamic cellular
13 energetic demands and thus impairment of PI3K function results in a profound homeostatic defect.
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